

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract. *In a modern technical University, learning English is an important component in the professional training of specialists for various sectors. The introduction of innovative methods of teaching English is increasingly relevant and very significant. The skillful combination of traditional teaching methods with the modern techniques makes the classroom atmosphere creative and increases students' motivation. The article presents a brief overview and analysis of modern information and communication technologies involved in the field of teaching English for specialized purposes.*

To date, a foreign language teacher at a technical university faces problems related to the methodology. The main feature of modern higher education is its humanitarian and personal orientation, when a special place is given to the formation of value-semantic formations of the personality and its spiritual and

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cultural growth. An integral part of the cultural process is the development of the values of world culture, which requires the study of foreign languages, mastering the language of other countries. The change in attitude to learning a foreign language is also associated with the processes of globalization, the expansion of Uzbekistan's ties with other countries, and the appeal to humanitarian values. In these conditions, knowledge of a foreign language makes it possible to expand intercultural communications, encourages people of different cultures to come into contact and conduct dialogues. In light of this, knowledge of a foreign language is a necessary condition for the professional development of future specialists in the system of higher education.

The analysis of practice has shown that the motivation of students in the process of learning a foreign language at a technical university is focused more on professional activity and to a lesser extent on personal self-determination and self-development.

Working in a non-linguistic university, a foreign language teacher should be well aware of the features of scientific and technical texts on the specialty being studied and, as necessary, acquaint students with them. First of all, it is the presence of special terminology, special general scientific vocabulary, specific service vocabulary, certain complex grammatical constructions.

The basis for learning in a non-linguistic environment will be a text in a foreign language. The teacher should choose those types and varieties of texts on the specialty being studied that will help the student to realize communicative opportunities [1].

Teaching oral speech in a foreign language, especially in a specialty in a non-

linguistic universality, is a complex and time-consuming process, since elements of the corresponding text genre, for example, scientific style, must be present in the student's speech.

When mastering the skills of oral speech in a foreign language in the specialty, it is necessary to remember that its monological element is not inferior to the dialogical one. Therefore, it is necessary to switch to increasing the volume of the monologue in the dialogue and later to purely monological forms of oral speech – summary, synopsis, annotation, description of the scheme, phenomenon or process – up to the recording of what was heard, which is useful when composing lecture notes and works. Naturally, this goal can be achieved only on the basis of communication-oriented textbooks and educational materials [2].

Teaching students a foreign language using personality-oriented technologies allows us to determine the conditions of their influence on the processes of professional and personal formation of future specialists. These conditions include the following:

- Learning a foreign language is filled with personally significant content that can form personal meanings of teaching, profession, life;
- The mechanisms of professional and personal development of students are being updated. (self-knowledge, self-esteem, self-affirmation, etc.);
- Implementation of cultural principles, professional competence, individualization is ensured;
- The priorities of the humanitarian-personal approach are realized when constructing training sessions, when a student acts as a subject, and his goal and prospects are professional and personal development as a future specialist.

Innovative approaches to teaching English appeared in response to the need for more effective facilitation and acceleration of the learning process [3]. This was caused by the growing popularity of the English language in a globalizing world. The claim for a single universal method, although advertised from time to time, has not been satisfied and is unlikely to ever be. Innovative non-traditional approaches arose "as a reaction to generally accepted assumptions about such things as the structure of various components of language or different types of text, about how language is processed in the head and used in interpersonal communication; about the nature of human learning and language learning in particular; about the nature of younger and older language learners and parameters such as memory, emotions, readiness, motivation and perception" [4].

If a teacher wants to be successful in his work with the group, he must find and adapt new technologies to involve students in traditional fields using multimedia learning tools and technologies from online resources and mobile applications. The mechanisms of teaching supersensible perception are developing faster and faster, and it is obvious that all modern trends should be covered.

Literature

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